

**ASSESSMENT OF PUBLIC RELATIONS STRATEGIES USED IN REPUTATION
MANAGEMENT OF SELECT INTERNATIONAL FOUNDATIONS IN FCT (ABUJA)**

Adefioye Ayobami Titilope

adefioyeayobami22@gmail.com

08030510497

Name: Prof M.S Rabi

Email: rabiums123@gmail.com

Specialization: Journalism and Media Studies.

Department of Mass Communication, Nasarawa State University Keffi.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15817476>

Abstract

Reputation management through strategic public relations plays a critical role in shaping the performance and credibility of non-governmental organisations. In Nigeria's development sector, competition among NGOs for donor funding and community trust has intensified, making effective communication and relationship-building essential for organisational sustainability and impact. This study examines the public relations strategies employed by Society for Family Health (SFH) and MacArthur Foundation in Abuja and their impact on reputation management. Using a mixed-methods approach, data was collected through surveys distributed to staff, volunteers, and stakeholders, alongside interviews conducted with PR heads from both organisations. The findings reveal that strategic public relations initiatives, such as community engagement programmes, donor relations, media engagement, and government relations, significantly influence stakeholder trust and organisational credibility. However, challenges such as inadequate funding (22%), lack of professional PR practitioners (25%), and underutilisation of digital platforms hinder the full potential of these strategies. The study highlights the need for NGOs to integrate comprehensive digital strategies, strengthen crisis management frameworks, and adopt more transparent communication models. The findings contribute to existing literature by providing insights into the effectiveness of public relations in fostering strong stakeholder relationships in Nigeria's NGO sector.

Keywords: *Public relations, reputation management, Nigerian NGOs, stakeholder engagement, community relations, donor relations.*

Introduction

The Nigerian non-governmental organisation sector plays a vital role in the country's development by providing essential services in health, education, and governance. However, as competition for donor funding and community support intensifies, NGOs must adopt strategies that foster stakeholder trust and organisational credibility. Public relations (PR) and reputation management are essential in achieving this objective. While PR helps shape an NGO's public image and stakeholder perception, reputation management ensures that organisations maintain long-term credibility and trust, ultimately enhancing sustainability and impact (Asemah, 2011; Seitel, 2001).

Reputation management encompasses the strategies NGOs use to build, maintain, and protect their organisational credibility. It involves managing stakeholder expectations, addressing public concerns, and demonstrating measurable impact through transparent communication (Bravo, Montaner, & Pina, 2009). PR, on the other hand, focuses on strategic communication and relationship-building with multiple stakeholder groups including donors, government agencies, communities, and media. This includes community engagement initiatives, crisis communication, media relations, and donor stewardship efforts (Asemah, 2017). Together, PR and reputation management shape how stakeholders perceive an NGO and influence their long-term support and engagement.

Society for Family Health (SFH) and MacArthur Foundation, two of Nigeria's prominent development organisations, are known for their distinct stakeholder engagement strategies. SFH focuses heavily on community-based health interventions and grassroots engagement, while MacArthur Foundation emphasises governance, justice reform, and policy advocacy through a combination of traditional and modern PR techniques (Asemah & Nwaoboli, 2023). Both organisations employ various PR initiatives, such as community outreach programmes, donor engagement activities, and media relations, to build and sustain strong stakeholder relationships.

Despite these efforts, Nigerian NGOs face several challenges in managing their reputation. Negative public perceptions caused by corruption allegations, inefficient programme delivery, and donor dependency have contributed to declining trust in the development sector (Adeniji,

Osibanjo, & Abiodun, 2013). Effective crisis communication is crucial to mitigating reputational risks and restoring stakeholder confidence (Brady, Arndt, & Amy, 2005). Additionally, community engagement initiatives play a significant role in improving public perception, as stakeholders tend to trust organisations that actively demonstrate impact and maintain transparent operations (Amponsah, Asamoah, & Isaac, 2015).

Technological advancements have transformed the way NGOs interact with stakeholders. Digital platforms, including social media, websites, and online reporting systems, offer organisations the opportunity to engage stakeholders directly and respond swiftly to their concerns (Nwaoboli, 2023). These platforms allow for real-time communication, transparent reporting, and programme promotion (Arijeniwa & Nwaoboli, 2023). However, digital communication also presents challenges, such as managing negative publicity and maintaining consistent messaging across platforms. If concerns shared online are not addressed promptly, they can significantly damage an organisation's reputation (Egbulefu & Nwaoboli, 2023).

Traditional media remains an essential PR tool for NGOs. Television, radio, and newspapers are widely used for programme promotion, crisis management, and reputation building. Organisations also leverage press releases, interviews, and community events to reinforce credibility and demonstrate impact (Fortunato, 2000). Despite efforts to enhance stakeholder engagement through PR and reputation management strategies, Nigerian NGOs continue to struggle with issues such as inconsistent communication, poor programme delivery documentation, and inadequate crisis response mechanisms. While some organisations leverage digital platforms for stakeholder engagement, others rely more on traditional methods, raising questions about the effectiveness of these strategies.

Existing studies suggest that well-executed PR initiatives can enhance reputation management, but there are gaps in understanding their full impact on stakeholder trust and organisational sustainability (Sarstedt, Wilczynski, & Melewar, 2012). This study seeks to assess how SFH and MacArthur Foundation manage their reputation through PR strategies and whether these efforts lead to improved stakeholder relationships and organisational credibility.

This study seeks to examine the public relations strategies employed by Society for Family Health and MacArthur Foundation in Abuja and their effectiveness in managing organisational reputation. Specifically, it aims to identify the PR approaches used by both organisations, evaluate their impact on stakeholder trust, and assess their role in strengthening reputation management. Additionally, the study explores the challenges that hinder the effectiveness of these strategies and how they influence overall stakeholder engagement.

The research is guided by four key research questions. First, it seeks to identify the public relations strategies adopted in reputation management by SFH and MacArthur Foundation in FCT. Second, it examines how these PR strategies help in promoting their reputation in FCT. Third, it evaluates the effectiveness of the PR strategies adopted for reputation management by both organisations. Fourth, it explores the challenges the PR departments encounter in managing their reputation.

Research Questions

The following questions have been formulated to guide the study:

1. What are the public relations strategies adopted in reputable management of the Society for Family Health and McArthur Foundation FCT?
2. How does the public relations strategies adopted by Society for Family Health and McArthur Foundation help in promoting their reputation in FCT?
3. What is the effectiveness of the public relations strategies adopted for reputable management of Society for Family Health and McArthur Foundation in FCT, Abuja?
4. What are the challenges the public relations departments of Society for Family Health and McArthur Foundation encounter in managing their reputation?

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Public relations is the practice of managing communication between an organisation and its various stakeholders to shape public perception and build strong relationships. It involves strategies such as media engagement, crisis communication, community relations, and reputation management (Asemah, 2011). In the NGO sector, public relations helps development organisations maintain credibility, address stakeholder concerns, and create a positive image (Seitel, 2001). NGOs use public relations to enhance trust by fostering transparent communication, managing crises effectively, and ensuring that stakeholders remain informed about programmes and impact.

Public relations activities in the NGO sector include media campaigns, community engagement, and brand positioning efforts that help organisations remain competitive for donor funding and community support. Effective public relations strategies allow NGOs to build credibility, attract donors, and differentiate themselves from other development organisations. Additionally, public relations efforts provide NGOs with the opportunity to influence policy by maintaining strong relationships with government agencies and development partners.

Reputation management refers to the strategic coordination of resources, personnel, and processes to build and maintain organisational credibility. It involves planning, monitoring, directing, and controlling communication activities within an institution (Bravo, Montaner, & Pina, 2009). In the NGO sector, reputation management plays a crucial role in ensuring sustainability, compliance with donor requirements, and stakeholder satisfaction. The development industry depends on sound reputation management practices to maintain stakeholder trust, secure funding, and enhance programme delivery. Strong reputation management practices contribute to an NGO's long-term success by ensuring donor retention, operational efficiency, and compliance with development standards (Sarstedt, Wilczynski, & Melewar, 2012).

In development organisations, effective reputation management ensures that public relations efforts align with organisational mission and values. PR managers collaborate with programme

leaders to create communication strategies that enhance visibility and stakeholder relations. Moreover, NGOs require efficient reputation management to navigate funding crises, political changes, and regulatory shifts that may affect operations.

Stakeholder relations involves the strategies and practices used by organisations to interact with and engage their various publics. It includes communication, relationship building, and transparent reporting. NGOs rely on stakeholder relations to build trust and encourage long-term support (Amponsah, Asamoah, & Isaac, 2015). Stakeholder relations management ensures that donors, communities, and partners receive timely information about programmes, concerns are addressed effectively, and service delivery meets or exceeds expectations. Strong stakeholder relations can lead to increased donor loyalty, reduced conflicts, and improved organisational reputation (Herington, Johnson, & Scott, 2006).

Effective stakeholder relations management in the NGO sector requires proactive engagement with multiple constituencies, including personalised donor stewardship and community participation programmes. Stakeholders are more likely to remain committed to organisations that prioritise transparency, communicate openly, and provide evidence of impact. NGOs that fail to implement strong stakeholder relations strategies risk losing support to organisations offering better engagement and accountability.

Crisis communication is a key function of public relations, particularly in the NGO sector, where trust and credibility are essential. Organisations engage in proactive communication, transparency, and rapid response initiatives to manage reputational crises. Studies suggest that development organisations with strong crisis communication strategies experience higher stakeholder confidence and organisational resilience (Brady, Arndt, & Amy, 2005). Negative incidents, such as programme failures or corruption allegations, require prompt and effective crisis communication to mitigate reputational damage (Khodarahmi, 2009). Crisis communication also involves monitoring public perception and responding to emerging issues that may affect stakeholder confidence in the organisation.

An NGO's reputation influences donor decisions, community support, and regulatory compliance. Public relations professionals monitor media coverage, stakeholder feedback, and sector trends

to ensure that the organisation maintains a positive image. Additionally, crisis communication plans enable NGOs to respond effectively to programme failures, security incidents, and other events that could harm their reputation. By investing in crisis communication, organisations can foster long-term trust and strengthen their position in the competitive development landscape.

NGOs adopt various public relations strategies to manage reputation effectively. One common strategy is media engagement, which involves using traditional and digital media to disseminate information and address public concerns (Fortunato, 2000). By maintaining an active presence in the media, organisations can shape public perception, promote transparency, and address stakeholder concerns more efficiently.

Community relations is another widely used strategy. NGOs invest in grassroots programmes to build goodwill and strengthen stakeholder relationships (Amponsah, Asamoah, & Isaac, 2015). Community engagement initiatives include participatory planning, local capacity building, public forums, and collaborative programming. Stakeholders are more likely to support organisations that demonstrate commitment to community development and empowerment.

Donor relations is essential in securing sustainable funding. Managing donor relationships through regular communication, transparent reporting, and impact demonstration helps maintain financial support (Herington, Johnson, & Scott, 2006). NGOs must develop donor stewardship frameworks that allow them to respond effectively to changing donor priorities and funding requirements.

Another key strategy is the implementation of stakeholder feedback mechanisms. By using surveys, community meetings, and online platforms, organisations can collect feedback and improve programmes based on stakeholder needs and expectations (Asemah & Nwaoboli, 2023). Listening to stakeholder concerns and responding promptly enhances trust and organisational credibility.

In addition, NGOs develop public relations campaigns to promote development awareness and responsible practices. These campaigns educate communities about health, governance, and economic empowerment while demonstrating the organisation's expertise and commitment. Such

initiatives strengthen stakeholder trust and demonstrate an NGO's contribution to national development.

Public relations plays a critical role in Nigeria's NGO sector, where stakeholder trust has been affected by past corruption scandals and ineffective programme delivery. Nigerian NGOs use public relations to engage with communities, manage crises, and promote new programmes and initiatives (Asemah, 2017). SFH and MacArthur Foundation, two of Nigeria's leading development organisations, have implemented strategic public relations campaigns to strengthen their market position and stakeholder confidence (Nwaoboli & Asemah, 2021). NGOs in Nigeria also leverage public relations to address regulatory concerns, improve development outcomes, and foster sustainable impact.

Nigerian NGOs rely on public relations to navigate political instability, funding fluctuations, and competition from emerging development actors. By using media relations, community engagement, and donor stewardship programmes, organisations can reinforce their commitment to development and demonstrate accountability. Additionally, Nigerian NGOs collaborate with government agencies, international partners, and civil society organisations to enhance their reputation and credibility.

Public relations in Nigerian NGOs also includes reputation crisis management, as development organisations often face challenges related to programme failures, political interference, and public skepticism. A well-structured public relations strategy helps NGOs maintain stakeholder confidence, manage negative publicity, and demonstrate transparency in their operations. Effective public relations efforts contribute to the stability and success of organisations operating in Nigeria's dynamic development landscape.

Review of Empirical Studies

Several studies have examined the impact of public relations strategies on reputation management in the NGO sector. Research conducted by Nwaoboli and Asemah (2021) analysed how digital public relations strategies, such as online media engagement, influence stakeholder trust and organisational credibility in Nigerian development organisations. Their findings suggest

that NGOs with strong digital presence tend to experience higher stakeholder satisfaction and improved public perception.

A study by Egbulefu and Nwaoboli (2023) explored the role of crisis communication in managing reputational risks in public institutions. The research found that organisations that adopt transparent and timely crisis communication strategies are more likely to retain stakeholder confidence during operational or reputational crises. This highlights the importance of proactive reputation management in the development sector.

Another relevant study by Amponsah, Asamoah, and Isaac (2015) examined how community engagement initiatives influence stakeholder relations in public health programmes. Their research found that stakeholders are more inclined to remain supportive of organisations that actively engage in participatory development activities, such as community health programmes and local capacity building. This suggests that community relations is an effective public relations strategy for fostering positive stakeholder relationships.

Asemah and Nwaoboli (2023) investigated the effectiveness of media relations in Nigerian NGOs. Their findings indicate that organisations that maintain good relationships with the media and regularly communicate through press releases and interviews experience better public perception and stakeholder retention rates.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-methods research design to gather and analyse stakeholder feedback on the public relations strategies used by the Society for Family Health and MacArthur Foundation for reputation management. The survey approach enabled the systematic collection of quantitative data regarding stakeholder perceptions, experiences, and satisfaction with both organisations' communication efforts. Both primary and secondary data sources were utilised. Primary data came from questionnaires administered to organisational staff, volunteers, and associates, alongside interviews with PR heads, while secondary data was sourced from relevant literature, organisational documentation, and online resources.

The study population consisted of current and former staff, volunteers, and associates from both NGOs residing in Abuja, Federal Capital Territory (FCT). According to organisational records, approximately 140 individuals were affiliated with both organisations as of December 2023, with SFH contributing 75 participants and MacArthur Foundation 65. These participants represented various operational units including administration, programme management, and capacity building. This population was chosen because they were directly involved in or affected by the organisations' public relations efforts and could provide firsthand feedback on the effectiveness, accessibility, and relevance of these communication strategies.

Due to the manageable population size of 140, a census sampling technique was adopted to ensure comprehensive coverage of all organisational members. This approach aimed to capture diverse organisational perspectives across different operational units. Additionally, purposive sampling was employed to select respondents from three key operational areas—administrative, programme management, and capacity building—to ensure representative coverage of different organisational functions and experiences with PR strategies.

Two primary research instruments were utilised. The first was a structured questionnaire designed specifically to capture stakeholder feedback on PR strategies. The questionnaire contained two main sections: Section A gathered demographic information including age, gender, educational qualification, organisational affiliation, and duration with the organisation. Section B comprised 15 items directly addressing the research objectives, using a combination of Likert scales, multiple-choice questions, and open-ended items to assess stakeholders' awareness, preferences, and satisfaction with various PR strategies employed by both organisations. The second instrument consisted of semi-structured interviews conducted with three PR heads from both organisations and a partner institution to gather qualitative insights into strategic decision-making and operational challenges.

The validity of the research instruments was established through content validation by three experts in public relations and organisational communication. Their feedback was incorporated to ensure the questionnaire and interview guide adequately addressed the research questions and were appropriate for the target population. For reliability testing, a pilot study was conducted with 20 participants who were not included in the final sample. Using Cronbach's alpha, the

questionnaire yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.78, indicating acceptable internal consistency and reliability for the study.

Questionnaires were administered through in-person distribution at both organisations' offices in Abuja. Research assistants were trained to help explain the purpose of the study and assist respondents who needed clarification. The data collection process achieved a 95% response rate (133/140), with three incomplete responses excluded, yielding 130 valid datasets for analysis. Semi-structured interviews were conducted face-to-face with PR heads and recorded with participants' consent. All ethical considerations, including informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation, were strictly observed throughout the data collection process.

The collected quantitative data were processed, coded, and analysed using descriptive statistics including frequencies and percentages presented in tabular format. Qualitative interviews were transcribed, coded, and thematically analysed using content analysis techniques, allowing for identification of recurring themes and insights that complement quantitative findings. The results were presented in tables to facilitate clear interpretation and discussion of findings in relation to existing literature and theoretical frameworks.

Findings and Analysis

Table 1: Public Relations Strategies Used in Reputation Management by SFH and MacArthur Foundation

Strategy	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Community relations	30	25
Media relations	3	3
Sponsorship of events	5	4
Government relations	4	3
Donor relations	16	14
All of the above	60	51
Total	118	100

Source: Field Survey 2024

A majority (51%) of respondents confirmed that both organisations utilise integrated PR approaches, combining multiple strategies for comprehensive stakeholder engagement.

Community relations (25%) emerged as the primary individual strategy, followed by donor relations (14%). However, media relations (3%) and government relations (3%) were significantly underutilised, indicating potential areas for strategic improvement.

Table 2: Effectiveness of PR Strategies in Enhancing Organisational Reputation

Effectiveness Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very effective	110	84
Moderately effective	12	9
Not very effective	8	7
Total	130	100

Source: Field Survey 2024

An overwhelming 84% of respondents rated current PR strategies as "very effective" in enhancing organisational reputation, indicating strong stakeholder confidence in both organisations' communication efforts. However, 16% reported limited to moderate effectiveness, suggesting room for improvement in certain aspects of reputation management.

Table 3: Challenges Faced in Applying Public Relations Strategies for Reputation Management

Challenge	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Lack of professional PR practitioners	33	25
Lack of functional PR unit or department	15	11
Management's attitude towards PR strategies	6	5
Lack of funds for PR strategies	30	22
All of the above	49	37
Total	133	100

Source: Field Survey 2024

The most significant challenges were lack of professional PR practitioners (25%) and insufficient funding (22%). A substantial 37% reported experiencing multiple challenges simultaneously, highlighting systemic barriers to effective PR implementation in the Nigerian NGO sector.

Table 4: Digital Platform Utilisation for Stakeholder Engagement

Digital Tool	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Social media platforms	30	25
Newsletters/press releases	6	5
Multimedia content	9	8
Comprehensive digital strategy	39	33
None of the above	46	29
Total	130	100

Source: Field Survey 2024

While social media (25%) was the most utilised digital tool, only 33% employed comprehensive digital strategies. Significantly, 29% reported no digital platform utilisation, indicating substantial underutilisation of available technologies for stakeholder engagement and reputation management.

Discussion of Findings

The analysis reveals that public relations strategies significantly influence reputation management in Nigeria's NGO sector. This aligns with findings by Asemah (2011), who emphasised the importance of strategic communication in building organisational credibility. Both SFH and MacArthur Foundation implement various PR strategies, including community engagement, donor relations, media engagement, and government relations, though with varying degrees of effectiveness.

The high utilisation of integrated PR approaches (51%) demonstrates sophisticated understanding of stakeholder communication, supporting Seitel's (2001) assertion that comprehensive PR strategies yield better outcomes than single-channel approaches. The emphasis on community relations (25%) aligns with Amponsah et al.'s (2015) findings on the importance of grassroots engagement for development organisations operating in diverse communities.

The exceptional effectiveness rating (84%) indicates successful reputation management, consistent with Bravo, Montaner, and Pina's (2009) research on the positive impact of strategic PR on organisational credibility. However, the underutilisation of media relations (3%)

represents a significant gap, particularly given Fortunato's (2000) emphasis on media engagement for organisational visibility and narrative control.

Qualitative interviews revealed critical insights into operational challenges. PR practitioners highlighted recurring difficulties in crisis management, with one respondent noting: "Limited resources often prevent us from responding quickly to emerging issues, which can affect our reputation." This observation aligns with Brady et al.'s (2005) emphasis on proactive crisis communication strategies and the need for adequate resource allocation.

Digital platform utilisation presents concerning results. While 25% actively use social media, the limited adoption of comprehensive digital strategies (33%) and complete non-utilisation by 29% suggests significant underexploitation of available tools. This finding resonates with Nwaoboli's (2023) observations about digital engagement challenges in Nigerian contexts, where resource constraints and expertise gaps limit optimal platform utilisation.

Structural challenges emerged as persistent obstacles, with 25% citing lack of PR professionals and 22% reporting funding constraints. These findings corroborate Adeniji et al.'s (2013) research on organisational resource allocation challenges in Nigerian NGO contexts. The absence of dedicated PR units (11%) further compounds these issues, suggesting that many organisations treat PR as an ancillary rather than strategic function.

The qualitative data revealed cultural and contextual factors influencing PR effectiveness. Respondents emphasised the importance of cultural sensitivity in stakeholder engagement, with one stating: "Understanding local customs and communication preferences is crucial for building trust in diverse communities like Abuja." This insight supports Asemah and Nwaoboli's (2023) findings on the importance of contextualised communication strategies in Nigerian settings.

Despite these challenges, both organisations demonstrate success in building stakeholder trust through their current strategies. The high effectiveness ratings suggest that foundational approaches in community and donor relations are working well, though opportunities exist for enhancement through digital integration and professional capacity building.

Conclusion

This study analysed the impact of public relations strategies on reputation management at Society for Family Health and MacArthur Foundation in Abuja. The results highlight that both organisations actively implement various PR strategies with notable success in building stakeholder trust and organisational credibility. While community engagement and donor relations have been highly effective, significant challenges remain in media relations, digital platform utilisation, and professional capacity development.

The findings reveal that strategic implementation of public relations initiatives significantly influences reputation management in Nigeria's NGO sector. Both organisations should enhance their media engagement strategies, develop comprehensive digital communication platforms, and invest in professional PR capacity building. By addressing resource constraints and adopting more integrated communication approaches, these NGOs can strengthen their reputation management and maintain a competitive advantage in Nigeria's dynamic development environment.

Recommendations

Key recommendations include developing proactive media relations programmes, investing in comprehensive digital strategies, implementing robust crisis communication frameworks, recruiting and training dedicated PR professionals, allocating adequate resources for PR activities, and establishing regular stakeholder feedback systems. Future research should explore the long-term impact of digital transformation on NGO reputation management strategies and examine comparative effectiveness across different African development contexts.

References

- Adeniji, A. A., Osibanjo, A. O., & Abiodun, A. J. (2013). Organisational change and human resource management interventions: An investigation of the Nigerian banking industry. *Serbian Journal of Management*, 8(2), 65-89.
- Amponsah, F. K., Asamoah, J., & Isaac, A. N. (2015). The role of public relations in enhancing customer satisfaction: The case of national health insurance programme in Mankranso. Christian Service University College, Department of Communication Studies.
- Asemah, E. (2009). Public relations and organisational management: An assessment of Jos International Breweries Plc. *JORIND*, 9(2).
- Asemah, E. (2011). *Mass media in contemporary society*. University Press.
- Asemah, E. S. (2017). *Community media for rural development communication: Principles, theories and practices*. Jos University Press.
- Asemah, E. S., Gujbawu, M., Ekhareafu, D. O., & Okpanachi, R. A. (2017). *Research methods and procedures in mass communication* (2nd ed.). University Press.
- Asemah, E. S., & Nwaoboli, E. P. (2023). Benin residents' perception of broadcast media coverage of the 2020 EndSARS protest in Nigeria. In E. S. Asemah (Ed.), *Communication, media and society* (pp. 282-289). Jos University Press.
- Brady, D., Arndt, M., & Amy, B. (2005). When your name is mud, advertise Companies in crisis used to lie low. The new response to bad press is positive spin. *Business Week*.
- Bravo, R., Montaner, T., & Pina, J. M. (2009). The role of bank image for customers versus the services sector. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 25(3), 190-201.
- Egbulefu, C. C., & Nwaoboli, E. P. (2023). Political digital advertising: Implications and way forward for Nigeria's 2023 general elections. *KIU Interdisciplinary Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4(1), 331-349.
- Egbulefu, C. C., & Nwaoboli, E. P. (2023). Twitter netizens perceptions of Nigerian government's public relations strategies in response to the Ike Ekweremadu organ trafficking crisis. *International Journal of Management, Social Sciences, Peace and Conflict Studies (IJMSSPCS)*, 6(2), 397-410.
- Fortunato, J. A. (2000). Public relations strategies for creating mass media content: A case study of the national basketball association. *Public Relations Review*, 26(4), 481-497.
- Herington, C. W., Johnson, L., & Scott, D. (2006). Internal relationships linking practitioner literature and relationship marketing theory. *European Business Review*, 18(5), 364-381.

- Khodarahmi, E. (2009). Strategic public relations. *Disaster Prevention and Management*, 18(5), 529-534.
- Nwaoboli, E. P. (2023). An appraisal of the political economy of the new media. *International Journal of Arts, Humanities and Management Studies*, 9(1), 38-47.
- Nwaoboli, E. P. (2023). Influence of Nigerian Television Authority (NTA), Benin City sports coverage on the development of sports. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Approach and Studies*, 10(1), 22-35.
- Nwaoboli, E. P., & Asemah, E. S. (2021). Textual analysis of select online media use of fear appeals in the promotion of COVID-19 vaccination in Nigeria. In E. S. Asemah (Ed.), *Communication, pandemic and civil unrest in Nigeria* (pp. 1-11). Franklead Printing Company.
- Sarstedt, M., Wilczynski, P., & Melewar, T. C. (2012). Measuring reputation in global markets: A comparison of reputation measures' convergent and criterion validities. *Journal of World Business*, 14(5), 1-11.
- Seitel, F. P. (2001). *The practice of public relations* (8th ed.). Prentice Hall.